

Part 2 - Literature Update

Section-1: Global Excerpts

Systematic Review of Meta-Analyses of Homeopathic Treatment - A Report

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Homeopathy is More Effective than Placebo

The debate about homeopathy and the placebo effect captivates a wide range of people, including both supporters and critics. The effectiveness of homeopathic medicine is a matter of contention with some individuals expressing strong conviction in their benefits, while others question their usefulness and point to modern scientific data to support their position. Central to this debate is the question: Does homeopathy work beyond the placebo effect - or are the observed therapeutic successes based solely on the expectation that it will help?

Dr. Harald Hamre and his colleagues have addressed precisely this question: **Is homeopathy more effective than placebo, or not?**

(The specific research question was: Does homeopathic treatment show positive effects across indications in meta-analyses of randomized, placebo-controlled trials that go beyond the placebo effect?)

A systematic review is a scientific work that evaluates the results of already existing studies. Strict methodical standards are applied in order to systematically identify and select these original studies and compile their results.

A meta-analysis is a statistical summary of the results from individual studies. This means that an overall statistical value is calculated to express how effective a given treatment has been on average. For such an evaluation to be meaningful, the studies must be similar in design and provide comparable data.

In a placebo-controlled trial, the effect of a drug is compared with that of a dummy drug (placebo). Participants do not know whether they are receiving the real drug or the placebo. This approach enables researchers to determine whether the drug being tested truly has an effect – in other words, whether it produces more than just the belief in its efficacy.

Methodological Approach

- * To answer this question, Hamre and colleagues investigated whether reliable scientific evidence exists for specific efficacy of homeopathy and how strong the effect is compared with placebo.
- * To do this, they used already published meta-analyses that summarized randomized, placebo-controlled trials on homeopathy across various indications.
- * These meta-analyses were subjected to a systematic review, i.e., the authors compared the studies using defined scientific criteria in order to obtain a clear picture of the current state of research. Only studies that met predefined criteria were included.
- * First, the researchers checked whether the authors of the meta-analyses had performed so-called effect estimates – that is, calculated how strong the effect of homeopathic treatment was compared to placebo. Based on these values, Hamre and colleagues then assessed the efficacy of homeopathy.
- * In addition, Hamre and colleagues evaluated whether the results of the meta-analyses are reliable or whether there are weaknesses that could limit their validity. Experts refer to this as the “risk of bias”¹. A low risk of bias means that the study results are likely to be reliable, i.e., they are unlikely to be distorted by methodological flaws or biased influencing factors.
- * Finally, Hamre and colleagues rated the overall reliability of the scientific findings. Experts refer to this as the “quality of evidence”, i.e., how convincingly the existing studies show that a treatment truly works and how confidently recommendations can be derived from them. This quality is classified into four levels: “high”, “moderate”, “low”, or “very low”².

**Hamre HJ, Glockmann A, von Ammon K, Riley DS, Kiene H. Efficacy of homeopathic treatment: Systematic review of meta-analyses of randomized placebo-controlled trials. *Systematic Reviews*. 2023;12:191. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-023-02313-2>.

Results

- * A total of six meta-analyses published between 1997 and 2017 were included in the review. The meta-analyses examined different approaches to homeopathy: Two dealt with individualized homeopathy (I-HOM)³, one with non-individualized homeopathy (NI-HOM) and three assessed both approaches together (ALL-HOM). In total, the six meta-analyses covered 182 individual studies on different indications.
- * In five of the six meta-analyses, the authors had calculated an overall effect estimate for all included studies. These five meta-analyses showed a statistically significant positive effect of homeopathy compared to placebo. The sixth meta-analysis did not perform such a calculation and therefore could not be included in the assessment of efficacy.
- * In four of the six meta-analyses, the authors also calculated an effect estimate restricted to studies of higher methodological quality⁴. Here, three of those four still showed significant positive effects of homeopathy. This result is particularly noteworthy because it demonstrates that the positive effect of homeopathy persists even when stricter selection criteria are applied and only the best studies in terms of methodology are considered. This underlines the reliability of the findings and makes them particularly scientifically robust. The fourth meta-analysis also found a positive effect, but it was no longer statistically significant.
- * Regarding methodological quality, three meta-analyses were rated as having “low risk of bias”, while three were rated as having a “high risk of bias”.
- * The assessment of the quality of the evidence revealed the following picture: The evidence for individualized homeopathy was rated as “high”. The evidence for non-individualized homeopathy and for both forms of homeopathy (All-HOM) combined was rated as “moderate”. After limiting the analysis to the three meta-analyses with a low risk of bias, the quality of the overall evidence for all forms of homeopathy was also rated as “high”, while the rating for individualized and non-individualized homeopathy remained unchanged. For comparison, an analysis of 608 Cochrane Reviews from 2013-2014 showed that 13% of the therapies examined achieved high quality of evidence, 31% moderate, 32% low, and 24% very low quality.

The following table summarizes the results:

Meta-analysis	Risk of bias	Form of homeopathy	Effect estimates for all included studies	Effect estimates for studies with higher quality	Positive effect homeopathy vs. placebo
Linde (1997)	low	ALL-HOM	yes	yes	significant
Linde (1998)	high	I-HOM	yes	-	-
Cucherat (2000)	high	ALL-HOM	yes	yes	significant
Shang (2005)	high	ALL-HOM	-	-	-
Mathie (2014)	low	I-HOM	yes	yes	significant
Mathie (2017)	low	NI-HOM	yes	yes	not significant

Conclusion and recommendation of the authors

The impetus for the systematic review by Hamre and colleagues

was the frequently expressed claim that homeopathy is no more effective than placebo. Over recent decades, several meta-analyses of randomized, placebo-controlled homeopathy trials have been published on this topic. However, these differed considerably – for example, in terms of which studies they included, how they assessed the quality of these studies, and which statistical methods they used. Consequently, the results also varied. To analyze these differences and to contextualize the existing body of research, Hamre and colleagues subjected the meta-analyses to a systematic review. In doing so, they have produced the first reliable, comprehensive overview of the current evidence on the efficacy of homeopathy.

They adhered to key scientific standards that are essential for high-quality systematic reviews, including a predefined and transparently published study protocol, an assessment of the methodological quality of the meta-analyses, and an evaluation of the quality of evidence according to recognized procedures.

Based on their evaluation, Hamre and colleagues conclude that homeopathy can produce positive effects beyond placebo. This finding aligns with laboratory experiments in which homeopathically potentized preparations have shown partly reproducible effects in physico-chemical, in vitro, plant, and animal experimental models.

Hamre and colleagues emphasize that homeopathy has a justified place in health care – and that, from a scientific perspective, there is no rationale for denying it.

Practical relevance

In every day clinical practice, prejudices against homeopathy surface repeatedly – both in conversations with patients and in professional practice exchange with colleagues. Common assertions include that homeopathic medicines contain no active substance, are therefore ineffective, and that any observed benefit is merely a placebo effect. Critics also frequently argue that there is no reliable scientific evidence supporting its efficacy.

The systematic review now provides a strong counterargument: it clearly shows that homeopathy is more effective than placebo.

Notably, the review is based on the best currently available evidence – meta-analyses of randomized, placebo-controlled trials – and was conducted and published in line with contemporary scientific standards.

Thus, it becomes evident that the research base for homeopathy is robust and offers a solid foundation for providing patients with well-grounded, scientifically supported information about the valuable contribution that homeopathic treatment approaches can make to health care.

1. The risk of bias was assessed using ROBIS (Risk of Bias in Systematic Reviews)
2. The quality of evidence is assessed using the GRADE method (Grading of recommendations, Assessment, development and Evaluation).
3. Non-individualized homeopathy included clinical homeopathy and complex homeopathy as well as isopathy.
4. For a study to be considered “methodologically higher quality”, it had to be classified as such by the authors in the meta-analyses based on at least three predefined quality criteria.

References

The following meta-analyses were included in the systematic review:

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